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Education and Society

वर्ष ४५, अंक १, ऑक्टोबर ते डिसेंबर २०२१

Year 45, Issue 1, Oct. to Dec. 2021

इंडियन इन्स्टिट्यूट ऑव्ह एज्युकेशन
जे. पी. नाईक पथ, कोथरुड, पुणे- ४११ ०३८

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Quarterly dedicated to the policy of 'Education through Social
Development and Social Development through Education'

‘सामाजिक विकासातून शिक्षण आणि शिक्षणाद्वारा सामाजिक विकास’
ह्या धोरणास वाहिलेले त्रैमासिक

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Editorial

We are very happy to publish our new issue No. 1 in 45th years of our quarterly journal 'Education and Society' ('शिक्षण आणि समाज'). In this issue, we have included twelve articles and research papers on different topics related to education, which are written by the scholars of different streams. We hope that the members and readers will appreciate this issue, which is helpful in gaining the knowledge and to motivate for contemplation of different dimensions of the education. We have included here five Marathi, one Hindi and six English articles and research papers in this issue.

In this century, we are thinking of total decolonization of education, self reliant education and autonomous education with online education system. Therefore we promote the writers, scholars and researchers in every field especially with education and social sciences for expressing to write for our issue. We are awaiting for the research papers and critical articles on the NEP 2020 regarding the implications of the same.

Along with we are expecting the writings on the issues of autonomy and education, online education, the role of virtual reality in education and the role of robotics in education for our future generation. As we know, we are thinking on the use of Artificial Intelligence in different fields of the human life, so we have to write on the same regarding the future human development with the help of education. We all know that the various new ideas, concepts and terminologies are coming in education for easy learning and decentralized education. We are expecting to expressions on the role of massive open online education. We have to write on these because all these are the flaming issues in current education.

In this issue we can read on the following topics.

Changing education policies and the role of the teachers, the facts and the reality of online education, the importance of Continuous Comprehensive Evaluation, the need of self learning, the skills of speeches in English, critics of Malayalam novels, the issue of self esteem among students, mental health and healthy family, protection of child rights, information literacy program, the inter relationship between the education and technology and attitude towards the sex education.

We hope that the readers will send their comments on the above different topics those are included in this issue. We will publish the opinions and the reactions of the readers in our next issue.

Please note that the opinions, conclusions and the findings of the researchers expressed in different articles and research papers are their own. The editor, executive editor and editorial board will not be responsible for the same.

-Executive Editor

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Self-esteem among Senior Secondary School Students of East Sikkim

T J M S Raju*
Anupam Pokhrel**

Abstract:

The present study aims to find the level of self-esteem among senior secondary school students of East Sikkim. The main objectives of this research is to study the general self-esteem, social self esteem, cognitive self esteem and total self esteem of senior secondary students of East Sikkim. The data were collected from 94 students of Sikkim by using standardized tool constructed by Sudha K. Sharma & Md. Sarwar (2015),The tool consists of 30 items divided into 3 areas i.e. (i) General Self-Esteem (ii) Social Self-Esteem and (iii) Cognitive Self-Esteem.The data were analysed with the help of statistical analyses by using Mean, S.D, and 't' ratio. The outcomes were deliberated according to the substantial values obtained. Based on the outcomes certain responses and conclusion were drawn.

Introduction:

Self-esteem impacts your decision-making process, your relationships, your emotional health and your overall well-being. It also influences motivation as people with a healthy, positive view understand their potential and may feel inspired to take new challenges. It is a fundamental human need. It creates a set of implicit expectations which is possible and appropriate to us. These expectations tend to generate the actions that turn them into realities. And the realities confirm and strengthen the original beliefs.

People with healthy self-esteem are having an understanding of their skills, they are able to uphold healthy relationships with others as they have a healthy association with themselves and they are having genuine and suitable expectations on themselves.

According to Woolfolk (2004),"It is accurately a product of our thinking and our actions, our values, ideas and beliefs as well as our interactions with others –then we see a significant role for the school. Practices that allow authentic participation, cooperation, problem solving and accomplishment should replace polies that damages self-esteem, such as tracking and competitive grading.

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According to Nathaniel Branden (1995) self-esteem is the disposition to experience oneself as competent to cope with the basic challenges of life and as worthy of happiness.

The Six Pillars of Self-Esteem:

Branden thought that self-esteem arises within us and is built on six practices that we take part in. He called the practices the Six Pillars of Self-Esteem, meaning that they backing the development of high self-esteem. The more we take part in these practices, the stronger our self-esteem would be.

1. The first pillar is the practice of living deliberately. This means that we're existing in each moment and aware of what's working on inside of us as well as around us. We don't overlook information that we don't like and we give attention to our emotions. People who are living at very conscious state are able to concentrate on what is happening now and stop over thinking about the past and the forthcoming.
2. Self-acceptance is the second pillar. It means that we accept ourselves completely. We are concerned ourselves even after we don't admire our own feelings or decisions. These features do not change our esteem for ourselves.
3. Self-responsibility: Self-responsibility means identifying that we're responsible of our own choices and activities and that no one else can style them, modify them or fix them for us. We don't blame any other to make us happy.
4. Self-assertiveness: Self-assertiveness is the fourth pillar. It's the exercise of worshipping our own needs and interests and of articulating them in appropriate ways. We know that it is nice to have certain needs and that is acceptable to let others know them in a healthy way.
5. Living purposefully: Living purposefully means living up to our goals. If we are holding purposefully, we set goals and we will plan accordingly and that will permit us to reach them. We need to live with these kinds of goals in our mind.
6. Personal integrity: The last pillar of self-esteem is personal integrity. We have beliefs about what behavior is appropriate and we keep our actions in line with that standard. You might end up this pillar by saying that we 'walk or talk.'

Shobhna Joshi and Rekha Srivastava (2009) conducted a study on self-esteem and academic achievement of adolescents. The study explains that boys have score significant higher on self-esteem related to girls. Significant gender variances were found in academic achievement. Girls were higher on academic achievement related to boys.

Moradi Sheykhjan, Tohid; Jabari, Kamran; Rajeswari, K. (2014) conducted a study on self-esteem and academic achievement of high school children. The resulting findings of this study indicated a very high correlation between academic achievement and self-esteem and concluded that there is significant positive correlation between self-esteem and academic achievement. There is no significant difference in self-esteem of boys and girls.

Orrie; Omrit & Kurman (2013) conducted a study on "Attachment, Self-esteem and test anxiety in adolescence and early adulthood". The purpose of this study was to assess how attachment dimensions, self-esteem and three subscales of test anxiety-cognitive obstruction, social derogation and tenseness are related in two age groups i.e. adolescents and college students. Results showed that college student revealed higher test anxiety than did high school students on the cognitive obstruction and tenseness scales.

Kaur & Gurpinder (2016) conducted a "study of self-esteem and emotional maturity of senior secondary school students". The present study has been designed to investigate the study of the self-esteem and emotional maturity of senior secondary school students. Further results revealed that there exists no significant difference between the self-esteem of male and female senior secondary school students and there exists a significant difference between the emotional maturity of male and female senior secondary school students.

Some of the studies revealed that both male and female are having problem with self-esteem and emotional maturity, (Orrie; Omrit & Kurman 2014). The study revealed that self-esteem is weaker among students with regard to their education level. Study conducted by Moradi Sheykhjan, Tohid; Jabari, Kamran; Rajeswari, K. (2014), shows that the self-esteem in boys and girls is almost the same and there is no significant difference. Boys score significant higher on self-esteem as compared to girls in the study conducted by Shobhna Joshi and Rekha Srivastava (2009).

Importance of the Study:

The scope of this study belongs to Sikkim state within four districts. When we look upon the historical perspectives of the state, Sikkim was merged as 22nd state of India in 1975. Going upon the growth of education process in the state, Sikkim was started with cultural education and after that growing continues at social front and institutionalized education through religious temples and to the modern formal institutionalized education centres called school. After the merger with India, many schools were established and gradually education developed in the state. However, still a fewer population in Sikkim state is following the monastic process of education in the state.

Further, going at this present scenario of education in the state, where little grooming and awareness is indeed required to understand the speedy growth of the world today, students who are at a school level and also at the edge of adolescence years are likely to get frizzle and influenced if they wouldn't understand the actual chaos of the world today. Such being the case, today's young generation is needed to be more self-esteemed to stabilize themselves from sceptic world. While to develop self-esteem, the students need to develop their positive attitude, control the feeling of low confidence, i.e., feeling of humiliation, grudge and feeling sarcastic, meantime students need to build a capacity of high confidence and joyfulness. Hence, the researcher has taken an attempt to measure the self-esteem level among senior secondary school students of Sikkim. The idea to conducting this study is to find out the key to identify what kind of impact and role played on self-esteem among senior secondary school students of Sikkim and this study has given an attempt to find out the root cause as well as the solution to provide them with proper guidance.

Objectives of the Study:

- To study the general self-esteem of senior secondary students of Sikkim with regard to their gender.
- To study the social self-esteem of senior secondary students of Sikkim with regard to their gender.
- To study the cognitive self-esteem of senior secondary students of Sikkim with regard to their gender.
- To study the total self-esteem of senior secondary students of Sikkim with regard to their gender.

Hypotheses:

The following null hypotheses have been set up for the study.

HO1: There is no significant difference between senior secondary school boys and girls of Sikkim with regard to general self-esteem.

HO2: There is no significant difference between senior secondary school boys and girls of Sikkim with regard to social self-esteem.

HO3: There is no significant difference between senior secondary school boys and girls of Sikkim with regard to cognitive self-esteem.

HO4: There is no significant difference between senior secondary school boys and girls of Sikkim with regard to total self-esteem.

Delimitations of the study:

The present study has been delimited to senior secondary school covering East district of Sikkim state.

Operational definitions of the terms:

Self-esteem - Self-esteem according to the present study refers as self-evaluation in academic aspects, self-worth in achievement and self-status among the group of senior secondary school students.

Senior Secondary School Student- Students studying in 11th – 12th class is considered as a senior secondary school student.

The Design:

The descriptive survey method has been used in the current research. It is considered to be an appropriate method because the evidences concerning the existing situation would be secured and norms would be identified to compare the present positions and also for the further plan of actions.

The Sample:

A sample of 94 senior secondary school students has been selected from the Sikkim state covering each district following. Out of 94 students, 47 girls and 47 boys has been selected from east district of Sikkim. Stratified random sampling technique has been used in the present study.

Tool used in the present Study:

Self Esteem Inventory constructed and standardized by Sudha K. Sharma & Md. Sarwar (2015) on Secondary & Senior Secondary school students. This tool consists of 30 items divided into 3 areas i.e. (i) General Self-Esteem (ii) Social Self-Esteem and (iii) Cognitive Self-Esteem.

Table 1.

The comparison across Gender on dimensions and on total Self-Esteem of Senior Secondary School Students of Sikkim is given below. (Boys-188, Girls-188, N=376)

Sr. No.	Variable	Gender	Means	SD	t-Values
1.	General self-esteem	Boys	32.74	4.24	5.11*
		Girls	27.47	5.65	
2.	Social self-esteem	Boys	28.47	4.59	5.32*
		Girls	24.04	3.38	
3.	Cognitive self-esteem	Boys	35.04	4.89	3.94*
		Girls	30.60	5.99	
4.	Total self-esteem	Boys	96.26	6.46	9.32*
		Girls	82.11	8.17	

*= Significant.

To find the difference in the scores in the self-esteem among boys and girls of senior secondary school students, the test of significance of difference between the means were calculated. The above table depicts the test significance of the dimension wise mean scores of emotional maturities.

The first dimension i.e. self-esteem among senior secondary school boys and girls. The calculated value for the "t" was found to be 5.11. The table value for the distribution is 1.96 at 0.05 level and 2.58 at 0.01 level, the calculated value for the distribution is significant at both 0.05 level and at 0.01 level. Thus the null hypothesis Ho: "There is a significant difference in general Self-esteem of boys and girls of senior secondary school student" is failed to accept the null hypothesis.

The second dimension i.e. self-esteem among senior secondary school boys and girls. The calculated value for the "t" was found to be 5.32. The table value for the distribution is 1.96 at 0.05 level and 2.58 at 0.01 level, the calculated value for the distribution is significant at both 0.05 level and at 0.01 level. Thus the null hypothesis Ho: "There is a significant difference in social self-esteem of boys and girls of senior secondary school students" is failed to accept the null hypothesis.

The third dimension i.e. self-esteem among senior secondary school boys and girls. The calculated value for the "t" was found to be 3.94. The table value for the distribution is 1.96 at 0.05 level and 2.58 at 0.01 level, the calculated value for the distribution is significant at both 0.05 level and at 0.01 level. Thus the null hypothesis Ho3: "There is a significant difference in cognitive self-esteem of boys and girls of senior secondary school students" is failed to accept the null hypothesis.

The total self-esteem among senior secondary school boys and girls found as the calculated value for the "t" was found to be 9.32. The table value for the distribution is 1.96 at 0.05 level and 2.58 at 0.01 level, the calculated value for the distribution is significant at 0.5 levels and significant at 0.01 level. Thus the null hypothesis Ho: "There is a significant difference in emotional maturity of boys and girls of senior secondary school students" is failed to accept at 0.05 and reject at 0.01 level.

Results: The result found significant difference between boys and girls in all dimensions of self-esteem. It means that both boys and girls are having differences on their self-esteem level in concerning to east district of Sikkim.

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